

PROVIDING EMPLOYMENT FOR THE POPULATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF SILK AND HOMEWORK IN FERGANA PROVINCE

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In our country, special attention is paid to the development of agriculture, especially cocoon breeding. 15-20 years ago, cocoons were raised once a year in our country, but as a result of the reforms implemented in the industry, silkworms are reared 3-4 times a year.

This effective method, launched since 2017, not only increases the "silver fiber" threshing floor, but also provides a permanent source of income to unemployed people through home farming. According to the press service of the Republican Women's Committee, more than 131,000 women were employed in our country during 5 months of 2018.

According to the source, by the beginning of 2018, there were 168,634 unemployed women in our country, and more than 131,000 of them had permanent and seasonal jobs. Among them, 29 thousand 785 women were involved in local enterprises and organizations, 8 thousand

ABSTRACT

This article focuses on the development of the silk sector in Uzbekistan, including the Fergana region, as a result of the increase in the volume of production and export, the establishment of home farming and the creation of seasonal and permanent jobs for the population, based on statistical sources.

679 were involved in family business, as well as home workers in silkworm care.

As a result of reforms carried out in the field of sericulture in our country, tutzors in Fergana region have been expanded year by year. In particular, in 2017, 31.9 hectares of new orchards were established, and by 2020, this indicator has increased to 432.5 hectares. In 2021, 492 hectares of new mulberry plantations were established in the region. In 2020, silk and silk products worth more than 6 million 965 thousand US dollars were exported by cocoon enterprises in the region. "Nurli tong silk", "Beshariq silk", "Dangara silk", "Silk word buseness", "Vodil silk spinning", "Saikali zamin", "Uchko'prik silk", "Toshloq silk", "Yozyovon" working in this direction New jobs were created on the basis of home farming in enterprises and cocooning clusters of "silk vats" LLC.

- We took care of two boxes of silkworms and harvested 98 kilograms. Akmaljon Abdusamatov, owner of the farm "Zarkent

zynati" in Toshloq district, says that he earned more than 4 million in one season.

In 2021, the first cocooning cluster was established in Sokh district of Fergana region. Initially, an agreement was signed with the representatives of the industry to feed silkworms in order to ensure their employment on the basis of household business with 17 unemployed women of the "Oftobro" community.

In our country, cocoons are grown once a year, and in this process, the entire population would be busy for 35-40 days. Today, cocoon growers earn income by continuously working in the industry for a period of 7 to 12 months.

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev, large-scale works were carried out in our country. In particular, specific tasks have been defined to ensure the interests of women, eliminate social problems that have plagued them for years, and increase women's employment. As a result of unemployment, women would go to other countries to look for work, their children would be left without care, and they themselves would face severe difficulties in foreign countries.

One of the five initiatives put forward by the President is aimed at solving this problem, providing women with full living conditions by ensuring their employment. In order to implement this initiative, joint-stock company "Uzbekpakhtasanoat" and "Uzbekipaksanoat" association plan to establish light construction sewing and knitting enterprises in each district and employ women.

"Uzbekipaksanoat" association also created seasonal and permanent jobs in the region.

The association aims to expand the production of silk products by organizing the process from cocoon cultivation to the production of finished products in a cluster method. This also created a great opportunity to attract women to work. In 2019, 30,000 jobs were created by the association in 2019 by involving women in home economics in Fergana region.

One year's service is written for the homesteaders who keep silkworms for one season. Earlier, the housekeepers were neither paid a salary nor recorded the length of service, but now, even if the women sit at home and feed silkworms as housekeepers, they are given the length of service. Or he had the opportunity to work at home, taking an order at a sewing company.

According to the President's decision PQ-224 adopted on 26.04.2022, tax and customs benefits are provided for subjects and enterprises engaged in the cultivation of silkworm seeds, mulberry seedlings and cocoons, cocoon processing and production of finished products. It was extended from January 1, 2023 to January 1, 2026.

According to the data of the State Statistics Committee, a total of 24,200 tons of cocoon raw materials were produced in January-September 2022. This is an increase of 6.4% compared to the same period last year.

The volume of cocoon raw materials grown in a cross-section of regions.

By regions	Tons
Karakalpakstan	802.1

Bukhara	2,574.4
Jizzakh	802.7
Kashkadarya	2,295.8
Navoi	1 022.2
Andijan	3 115.2
Namangan	2,031.5
Samarkand	3 122.6
Surkhandarya	1,832.1
Syrdarya	665.6
Tashkent	1,710.4
Ferghana	2 241
Khorezm	2 015.3
TOTAL	24.2

In order to ensure the employment of the population and create a permanent source of income for them, household jobs were created in the field of cocooning in the region, and it was planned to care for 5 thousand 870 boxes of silkworms in the autumn season of 2022 cocoon cultivation in the Fergana region. This year, more than 97,000 unemployed people were provided with employment, home-breeding contracts were concluded, and silkworm seeds were revived in 28 incubators and distributed to home-breeders. In 2023, it is planned to increase this indicator from 100 thousand.

12 boxes of silkworms were taken care of during the season by farmers and householders in "Kurgoncha" neighborhood of Rishton district of the

region. In this way, employment of 26 women was ensured and family income increased.

- 420 boxes of silkworm seeds were distributed in the district, and it was planned to grow 40 kilos of cocoons from each box. According to this plan, employment of 830 householders was ensured.

CONCLUSION. In 2022, cocooning clusters in Fergana region exported processed silk raw materials worth 9 million 254 thousand US dollars. In the region, great attention is being paid to bringing the cultivation of "silver fiber" to new levels, strengthening the food base for silkworms, and creating conditions for the people who want to do homemaking to work at home.

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